

Performance Measurement of Openness in Transport Research

K Palts¹, A Akac², A Anagnostopoulou^{2*} and J Michelmann³

¹ Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR), Linder Höhe, Köln 51147, Germany

² Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Hellenic Institute of Transport, G.Kasimati 1 str., Piraeus 18531, Greece

³ VDI/VDE INNOVATION + TECHNIK GMBH (VDI/VDE), Steinplatz 1, Berlin 10623, Germany

E-mail: a.anagnostopoulou@certh.gr (Afroditi Anagnostopoulou)

Abstract.

Open Science in transport research sector is a challenging activity since it covers a wide range of aspects, from evaluation of research, open access to research results, and relevant data infrastructures, all aiming at making science more efficient, better reproducible and more responsive to societal and economic expectations. This paper aims to identify key performance indicators (KPIs) for assessing Open Science in transport in terms of validity or not. The main objective is to determine proper criteria and measures that will be used to evaluate the performance of Open Science in transport research. Their monitoring and analysis will enable knowledge and understanding of Open Science in transport research by providing guidance for defining effective KPIs at both operational and strategic level.

Keywords: key performance indicators, open science, transport, criteria, recommendations.

1. Introduction

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are important measure to evaluate the success of a process as well as implementation of a change. The Open Science and the European Open Science Cloud initiative are paving the way by proposing guidelines for successful implementation, as well as for the Open Science, proposing a unanimous set of KPIs are required in order to allow knowledgeable decisions. In European level for Open Science, the development of detailed list of KPIs is still work in progress. One of the main challenges is to harmonise the Open Science related activities in various sectors and to create synergies. In order to answer the challenge – European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) was initiated to better regulate and to provide guidelines and recommendation. Nevertheless, each sector is addressing unique issues, related to implementation of Open Science. Therefore, for successful execution of the task – development KPIs in the transport sector, analyses are needed, based on the secularities of the sector and considering available regulations to develop the custom set of KPIs.

The European Commission (EC) regulation recommendation on access to and preservation of scientific information, published on 2018 supports the cooperation in between academia and researchers. Together with the national regulation implementation, fostering measuring and rewarding system is foreseen [1]. This highlights the importance of the rewarding system and should be included as a main factor while developing KPIs for transport research data. Further analysis is needed to see how measuring a rewarding system could be successfully implemented and monitored in Transport research sector. For general Open Science Metric “*new generation metrics*” are being developed. To support the activity, at European level, a working group has been established, the so-called Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP) whereas topics such as Altmetrics, including bibliometrics for measuring publication in social media are continuously being discussed [2].

In 2019, an expert group by European Commission put in place: “*Indicator Frameworks for Fostering Open Knowledge Practices in Science and Scholarship*” [3]. The group elaborated a set of recommendations dealing with the following dimensions:

- Monitoring (implementation of Open Science practices)
- Learning (knowledge about Open Science publications)
- Resource allocation and career assessment.

As a first step, the identification of key stakeholders plays a significant role. Furthermore, KPIs support and ensure efficient processes for the stakeholders as a mean of communication within stakeholders to inform them about improvement of endeavors, enabling to create a trustworthy environment and generate an attractive system for them [4]. The Open Science Roadmap points out three main categories for enabling Open that need to be fostered; (i) transparency, (ii) sustainability and (iii) collaboration [5]. European Open Science Cloud Strategic and Research Innovation Agenda (EOSC SRIA) identified 14 Action Areas (AA) - the gaps that need to be addressed and priorities where action is needed for the development of proposed KPIs in Open Science in Transport Research (OSTR) [6]. KPIs should refer to the FAIR principle. For FAIR Data, the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group has published a model with 41 criteria, which allows to compare data with the FAIR principles and to be assessed. It addresses a degree of priority: essential, important, useful. In the same way, EOSC latest update lists that the FAIR principles are a recent concept so metrics are still under definition. The Metrics and Certification Task Force of the EOSC FAIR Working Group recommends that the definition of metrics should be a continuous process, regularly tested and iterated to minimize these risks [7].

During the implementation of EU H2020 BE OPEN project created a set of tools (TOPOS Observatory and Forum) to Promote, Regulate and standardize Open Science in transport. The core objectives of TOPOS Observatory and Forum are focused on limiting existing barriers in Open Science in Transport Research and aligning transport research with EOSC by following FAIR principles [8]. There are some altmetrics – alternative metrics, used in TOPOS for measuring societal impact and to foster Open Science. The list of available altmetrics in TOPOS is listed at Figure 1.

Figure 1. TOPOS Categories for Altmetric

2. Key stakeholders

In an attempt to monitor and assess the performance and the validity of implementing initiatives (i.e. actions and policies) of OS in a systematic way, a two-step methodology is defined to ensure the relevance to as well as the commitment of the relevant stakeholders (Figure 2). Criteria that could be quantified by proper KPIs are developed in order to support monitoring and evaluation. Within the evaluation stage, performance measurements will be utilized to revise properly actions and policies based on the results derived from the KPIs supporting decision making regarding OS in transport research.

Figure 2. Methodology for assessing Open Science initiatives in transport research

The end users in transport research involve both individuals and organizations. The priorities of transport stakeholders address the needs and objectives of end users in transport research sector. In more detail, organizations could be either private or public and there are 3 main different categories which represent industry, research community and society by summarizing the criteria for promoting OS in transport research linked to the mentioned categories of end users. The proposed criteria are based on the opportunities of OS at national and institutional level in Europe as they are presented in the deliverable 5.1 of the BE OPEN Project [9]. Individual users are displayed in Figure 4 [10].

Figure 3. Different categories of end users

Figure 4. Individual users

3. KPIs for performance measurement of OS initiatives in transport research

Measuring the performance of the current actions and policies using proper KPIs evaluates their impact assessment supporting decision making regarding OS in transport research. The KPIs evaluate comprehensively the performance of the applied actions and policies, and quantify the criteria of end users for promoting OS in transport research. The proposed KPIs are defined to assess the different criteria of both private and public stakeholders.

Open Science data Monitoring (OSM) – standing for provision of data and insights to support the implementation process – should also be considered in Transport research Data. We need to develop indicators, general as well as area specific, to monitor the implementation of the policies. This is not an easy task due to fragmentation and quantity of available data [11].

Figure 5. Open Science consist of openness in several different areas [12]

TOPOS Observatory and Forum provide valuable resources and **collaboration** to a wide range of users (individuals and organizations) in transport research from the public and private sector. They enhance **visibility of results** as well as the **reputation of individual researchers** presenting their citations, defining a reputation score and presenting the total number of their views. In addition to the TOPOS tool developed within BE OPEN project, the TRIMIS tool is another **good practice** of Open Science in transport research even though it covers only research outcomes of the Strategic Transport Research and Innovation Agenda (STRIA).

The **models and methods sharing and improvement** are determined by the TOPOS interoperability which supports a wide range of sources in transport research such as publications, research data, software and other as well as by the TOPOS Forum which supports collaborative ways of working and exchange information among transport researchers in Europe. Exchange knowledge specifies the total number of researchers who are incentivized to perform Open Science in transport sector and how TOPOS tool makes European transport research increasingly discovered and reused. The validation of data of TOPOS tool is ensured as the available research data were produced by publicly funded research in Europe which are officially approved by the funding agencies.

The identified opportunities and barriers, BE OPEN Task 5.1 are significant as they give valuable input to policy makers to provide/ develop/ publish/ support the community by supplying recommendations: the so- (policy drivers). To foster Open Science, it is important to tackle the issues with emphasis on market exploitation of research which could be a de-accelerator to the establishment of OS.

Thus, the proposed KPIs have been built upon BE OPEN D5.2 where the challenges, opportunities and barriers were identified and analysed. The goal of KPIs is to develop a set of metrics which are aimed to measure and monitor Open Science implementation in the transport (research data) sector. Based on that, a short summary of the most important barriers, challenges and opportunities is concluded on the following picture.

4. Challenges and opportunities oriented KPIs

4.1. Opportunities/Operational (oriented) KPIs

Concerning KPIs for TOPOS, criteria for Stakeholders were defined, based on the Open Science in transport research opportunities, defined in D5.1 and shown in Figure 6 [13]. KPIs are then conceived

as a set of performance measurements demonstrating how effectively TOPOS is achieving key objectives per year. The definition of KPIs will focus on the challenges and opportunities. The barriers do not contain aspects that could be turned into defined indicators.

Figure 6. Barriers, Challenges and opportunities of OS at national and institutional level

Table 1. KPI examples based on assumed stakeholder relevance

		End-Users		
		Organizations		
Individuals		Technology Platforms	Research Organizations	Public Authorities
Criteria	• Data sharing	• Data sharing		
	• Models and methods sharing and improvement	• Models and methods sharing and improvement		
	• Exchange knowledge	• Exchange knowledge		
	• Validation of data/sources	• Validation of data/sources		
	• Good practices	• Good practices		
	• Collaboration of researchers	• Collaboration of research organizations		
	• Visibility of results	• Visibility of results		

- Enhance reputation of researchers

- Enhance reputation of research organizations

Table 2. KPIs for performance measurement of OS in transport research

Category	Performance Measurement of OS in Transport Research	Indicator	Description
	Field of action	KPI	Motivation (What & Why)
Data Sharing	Transport researchers performing publicly funded research make relevant results available, as openly as possible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of authors in TOPOS • Number of projects being published 	Number of authors in transport research, who make data openly available, by monitoring the increase per year.
	Associations of transport research sector performing publicly funded research make relevant results available, as openly as possible.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number Associations • Number of projects by associations 	Number of Associations in Transport research, who make data openly available, monitoring by increase per year.
	Research organizations of transport research sector with formal standards for data sharing and reuse.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of data FAIR compliant • Number of FAIR standards approved by year 	(Chapter 1) the following criteria should be met [14]: F- assigned PID A – metadata available I – compatible data format (pdf or other R – data format can be reused
Models and methods sharing and improvement	(a) TOPOS Observatory supports the interoperability of a wide range of sources in transport research such as publications, research data, software and other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of various publications in The TOPOS Observatory • Number of users for TOPOS Forum and number of contributions 	Measuring (yearly) different publications, for example research data, software and other.
	(b) TOPOS Forum supports collaborative ways of working and exchange information among		Measuring (yearly) the number of registered users and contributions in the TOPOS Forum

	transport researchers in Europe.		
Exchange knowledge	Researchers are incentivized to perform Open Science in transport sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of a contribution rating system • Number of Credentials (ECTS, EOSC specified credentials) delivered through OS training activities. 	<p>Creating a possibility to rate the contributions</p> <p>How often the TOPOS publication/ from a user was cited</p> <p>Number of ECTS/ credentials</p>
	Strengthen the exchange within the community of European transport research in line with the objective of Horizon Europe to foster Open Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of uploads in the context of projects granted by the EC (e.g. Horizon Europe) & views by EU-projects participants 	Number of uploads of projects granted by EC each year
	European transport research is increasingly discovered and reused as a result of TOPOS tool.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of views and citations of TOPOS content 	Yearly increase of number of views and citations of TOPOS content
Validation of data	Transport Research data produced by publicly funded research in Europe are valid by default and TOPOS includes this information.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of publicly funded projects listed/ published in TOPOS • Number of publicly funded openly available datasets 	Establishing central source (TOPOS) for validated data from publicly funded research per year
Good practices (guidelines)	TOPOS follows Transport Research and Innovation Agenda (STRIA) that outlines future transport research and innovation (R&I) priorities to decarbonize the European transport sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of publication uploads in the areas of the STRIA • Number of access for a publication • Number of transport-based 	<p>TOPOS - effectiveness for research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers can upload – central “database” • Central “database” for information research

		publication (air, road, rail, maritime, multimodal)	
	TOPOS tool is operational and provides relevant services, information and data to support transport researchers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey among community 	TOPOS provides services to support transport research activities
Collaboration of researchers	TOPOS Observatory is a valuable resource to a wide range of users (individuals and organizations) in transport research from the public and private sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall number of users • number of PPPs created through the Forum (projects, MoUs, agreements) • number of citations of TOPOS publications • % of publication from open PPP results 	<p>Monitoring the increase of number of TOPOS users and the number of citations of TOPOS publications.</p> <p>Indicator that defines the analogy of open source datasets/results coming from completed or ongoing PPP projects</p>
	TOPOS Forum is a valuable collaboration tool to a wide range of users (individuals and organizations) in transport research from the public and private sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of registered individuals and number of registered organisation 	Monitoring number of different users in TOPOS Forum for supporting researchers finding new collaboration partners
Visibility of results	TOPOS is populated with valuable interoperable information and data about transport research.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of TOPOS publications with readership activity • Number of citations 	Monitoring user activity and the number of citations to evaluate TOPOS visibility per year.
Enhance reputation of researchers	TOPOS supports researchers to enhance reputation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of citations • Reputation score 	<p>Measuring the citation and analyzing the score and number of views we can value the TOPOS attractivity to enhance reputation of researchers.</p> <p>A score can be invented through the community</p>

4.2. Strategic (oriented) KPI-s to react to challenges

Furthermore, for Operational KPIs, such as identifying proper KPIs for TOPOS, there are also strategic KPIs needed to be listed, to measure the Open Science implementation in transport Research. This could be done by monitoring the challenges/ developing KPIs to monitor the Challenges/ How successful originations are by overcoming the challenges for Open Science in transport research (Figure 7). There is a need for an integrated approach of Open Science Monitoring. Therefore, Transport Research Data KPIs have been developed in coherence with EOSC.

Figure 7. Barriers, Challenges and opportunities of OS at national and institutional level

In order to monitor Open Science implementation in transport research data and to propose proper KPIs to measure the success, the identified challenges were used for categorization and for main focus, as to overcome the challenges is the most important part. This has been pursued by identifying and monitoring the process for finding solution for challenges.

For assessment of the successful implementation of the Open Science in the transport research, the TOPOS Observatory and TOPOS Forum are good tools to measure the proposed KPIs. In addition, the stakeholders – as main users – are also playing a vital role whereas the resources and organizational issues are one of the main challenges to consider. Monitoring the implementation of Open Science in organizations ensures the successful OS implementation in the transport sector. Due to complex nature of transport research data, not all the challenges are being analysed and included in the list of developed KPI-s. The Task 5.2 team concluded that the main challenges is related to resources and organizational issues, as well as this is one of the main influencers for the TOPOS Observatory and Forum and should

be monitored. Main challenges are described in the following table (see Table 3) and the following KPIs are addressing the challenges illustrated above (see Table 4):

Table 3. Challenges for Open Science implementation

Categories	Challenges
1. Resources and organizational issues	1. Qualified staff, available software, reputation of researchers, exchange knowledge, cooperation, recognition, Co-authorship to other researchers' publications using their data, cost
2. Marketing for making the open data known and addressing branding issues	2. Models and methods for information sharing, format of publication, database design, DOI, IPR

Table 4. KPIs addressing challenges of Open Science in transport research

Category	Performance Measurement of OS in Transport Research	Indicator	Description
	Field of action	KPI	Measuring/ Motivation
Resources and organizational issues	Open Science implementation in organization: available Process and qualified staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of organisation with a process in place for integrating Open Science activities. • Number of organisations of continuous training process for Open Science experts • Number of organisations with a process in place to support Mentoring and Supervision in Open Science • Number of researchers taking part in a mentoring/supervisor program for Open Science (How many participants in mentoring/ supervision program/per year 	<p>Training researchers in Open Science principles and methods; Developing curricula and programs in Open Science methods, including Open Science data management; Raising awareness and understanding in Open Science in undergraduate and “Does your organization have a process in place for integrating Open Science activities?” (y/n) masters’ programs.</p> <p>“Do you have continuous training process for Open Science experts?” (y/n)</p> <p>Mentoring and encouraging others in</p>

		developing their open science capabilities/ Supporting early stage researchers to adopt an open science approach. “Do you have a process in place to support Mentoring and Supervision for Open Science” (y/n)
FAIR metrics & certification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commonly agreed stamp/certification for repositories containing above X % of OS tools and open/FAIR data • % of transport research organizations/associations have policies which require FAIR principles to be implemented via a defined Data Management Plan • % of transport research organizations/associations have FAIR datasets deposited in their repositories (or ones they use) • % of transport research organizations/associations have FAIR datasets deposited in their repositories (or ones they use) 	FAIR standards approval by transport research organizations Establishing open and fair in organisational repositories
Promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of dissemination channels (website, portals, blogs, social media channels, open repositories, etc.) used to promote organization’s open transport research activities 	Communication tools used for open dataset/publications/software promotion Thematic OS workshops for a specific transport mode/competence area could be organized

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of mentions of TOPOS in social media • Number of transport research publications mentioned in social media • Number of overall events promoting OS in transport research initiatives. 	
Marketing for making open data initiative known and addressing branding issues	Ensure Data Ownership and IPR [15]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of TOPOS datasets which are compatible with EOSC licensing model 	To ensure data ownership and IPR for Transport Research Data following aspects need to be measured to ensure compatibility with EOSC Licensing model Increase/yearly
	Opening up commercial information in the public interest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of data related articles yearly published by transport organizations • Number of organisations making data sets publicly available 	To monitor the development of open innovation and foster applied science transparency in Europe, it would be possible to measure the articles and data sets that contains commercially relevant information of public interest

5. Conclusions

In an attempt to ensure the long-term implementation of Open Science in transport research, the commitment of relevant stakeholders should be determined. For this reason, the proposed KPIs for the performance measurement of efficient Open Science tools in transport research provide guidelines suitable for the stakeholders of both private and public sector in order to assess how Open Science is implemented in transport research domain. The main goal is to support the assessment of critical success factors such as transport research policies, transport research projects per mode of transport, transport research infrastructures and software per mode of transport or per EU country members, transport research publications per mode of transport/research policy etc.

Analysing the main objectives and priorities, eight main criteria were defined that cover the different categories of end users. Based on these criteria, a set of KPIs (both quantitative and qualitative) were developed to assess and measure the performance of the implemented set of Open Science actions. Each indicator belongs to one of the predefined criterion that determines the motivation (what & why) and the field of action. Therefore, an indicator may concern one or more end users referring to their objectives and priorities. Besides the KPIs identification, consideration should be also given on the evaluation methodology used for assessing the impact of the implemented actions. Towards this

direction, a critical research pointer is the study of the methodologies used in other sectors for analyzing and evaluating their KPIs.

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